

The Impact of Diabetes Mellitus on Nerve Conduction: A Cross Sectional Research

Raj Kumar¹, Shalini Rastogi², Shivani Sharma³, Shams Aaghaz⁴, Sonal Rastogi⁵

¹Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, National Capital Region Institute of Medical Sciences, Meerut, UP, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, School of Medical Sciences and Research, Greater Noida, UP, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, National Capital Region Institute of Medical Sciences, Meerut, UP, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Physiology, National Capital Region Institute of Medical Sciences, Meerut, UP, India

⁵Postgraduate Resident, Department of Pedodontics, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida, UP, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Shams Aaghaz

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Diabetic peripheral neuropathy is a severe condition that lowers quality of life and has social repercussions. Early diagnosis and treatment of neuropathic processes might change their trajectory and significantly lower the morbidity and death that go along with them. This research investigates the impact of long-term control of blood sugar on diabetic peripheral neuropathy in individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes.

Material and Methods: From July to September of 2023, a hospital-based research was conducted at the NCR Medical College Hospital in Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India. Those who had Type 2 diabetes for less than ten years and were older than eighteen were all recruited. The BMI, HbA1c level, as well as nerve conduction studies (NCS) were determined using established methods. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS), version 25.0, was used to analyze the data. A P-value of less than 0.05 was deemed significant.

Results: Fifty-two of the 95 T2DM patients were men. According to our research, the sensory velocity decreased from 64.069 ± 3.221 to 54.001 ± 5.339 and the motor nerve decreased from 63.391 ± 2.379 to 53.869 ± 2.081 ($P = 0.0501$, $P = 0.0031$, respectively) as the length of diabetes increased. Furthermore, a significant reduction in motor nerve amplitude from 8.789 ± 3.109 to 6.941 ± 1.839 ($P = 0.0501$) and sensory nerve amplitude from 25.711 ± 5.701 to 19.511 ± 6.509 ($P = 0.0031$) was seen with longer duration of diabetes. Additionally, when HbA1c was greater than 6, all NCS parameters (amplitude and velocity) reduced: motor velocity dropped from 63.001 ± 2.589 to 51.439 ± 1.661 ($P = 0.021$), and sensory velocity declined from 63.961 ± 2.359 to 55.489 ± 2.431 ($P = 0.029$). Moreover, the motor amplitude dropped from 6.879 ± 3.551 to 6.609 ± 3.289 ($P = 0.0509$), whereas the sensory amplitude dropped from 26.909 ± 1.261 to 20.849 ± 2.101 ($P = 0.0509$). Furthermore, there is a significant ($P = 0.0509$) link between the BMI and the motor and sensory amplitudes.

Conclusion: All of the nerve conduction testing parameters were negatively impacted by high BMI and poorly treated (high HbA1c) long-term diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus; Nerve Conduction; Peripheral Neuropathy.

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Introduction

Individuals with diabetes mellitus (DM), a metabolic disorder, are more likely to experience microvascular and macrovascular complications [1]. The number of diabetic complications will undoubtedly rise as the global diabetes epidemic spreads. One of the repercussions of diabetes is peripheral neuropathy, which can have major

negative effects on social, economic, and quality of life aspects [2]. Diabetic neuropathy (DN) affects 1.91% of diabetics worldwide [3]. DN varied from 21.9% to 60% in Northern Africa. [4] Awadalla (2017) calculated that 68.2% of Sudanese people had diabetic polyneuropathy [5]. One of the risk factors that is most closely linked to the

development of diabetic neuropathy (DN) in individuals with type 2 diabetes (T2DM) is poor glucose management [6]. Good glycemic management and early diagnosis of diabetic neuropathy can dramatically change the disease's course and reduce morbidity and death. Type 2 diabetes and degenerative DN may expedite the age-related decline in strength and muscle mass by affecting inflammation and metabolism. This detrimental cycle of diabetes and ageing will consequently accelerate the decline of autonomy and intensify the onset of limits associated with everyday living activities. [7] The length of DM and glycemic management was found to have an impact on DPN in individuals with type 2 DM. The research's conclusions and outcome will highlight the need of managing diabetes mellitus early on in order to mitigate or postpone the pathophysiology that leads to PDN.

Aim and Objectives

This research investigates the impact of long-term control of blood sugar on diabetic peripheral neuropathy in individuals diagnosed with type 2 diabetes.

Material and Methods

This was a cross-sectional research conducted in a hospital. The study was conducted at the NCR Medical College Hospital in Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India, between July and September of 2023. Every participant gave written, informed permission. Participants received the results of the parameters that were assessed.

This study comprised 95 patients with a 10-year diagnosis of T2DM who were above the age of 18. Exclusion criteria included those with type 1 diabetes, known etiologies of peripheral neuropathy, such as neuromuscular disorders, genetic neuropathy, and alcoholic patients with a history of myopathies, drug-induced neuropathy, known-cause peripheral neuropathy, and cerebrovascular stroke. [8]

Anthropometric Measures: Using a calibrated weight and height measuring instrument in accordance with approved protocols, weight was determined. BMI was computed using the following formulas: height squared in meters times' body weight (in kgs).

After meeting the selection criteria, BMI was categorized as follows in kg/m²: 18.5–24.9 was considered normal weight; 25–29.9 was considered overweight; 30–34.9 was classed as obese I; 35–39.9 as obese II; and ≥ 40 as obese III.

Chemical Analysis: Under sterile circumstances, five millilitres of venous blood were extracted from each participant's antecubital vein. The NycoCard©Reader, a specially designed enzyme-

linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) reader, was used to measure each participant's HbA1c levels.

Electrophysiological Investigation: One technician conducted nerve conduction studies (NCS) using standard techniques [7]. For NCS, a surface stimulator called the Neurowerk EMG system electromyography (Neuroevolution, Sistemas Medicos Lda, Germany) was used. 10 mm diameter circular disc electrodes were used to record potentials. Both the upper and lower limbs were used in the test. Sensory and motor amplitudes, as well as distal motor and sensory latencies, were assessed. We received at least ten responses on average. The gadget computed the amplitudes and latencies automatically. To determine the motor and sensory conduction velocity (CV), divide the observed distance by the onset latency.

Upper limbs nerve conduction measurements:

Both the motor and sensory nerves of the upper limbs were assessed; the radial nerve was tested for sensory solely, and the median and ulnar nerves for both motor and sensory functions. The medial motor nerve was evaluated with the help of an electrode. The electrode was positioned midway between the first metacarpophalangeal joint and the distal wrist crease. The electrodes for the extensor carpi ulnaris were placed on the thumb and in the middle of the forearm, whereas the electrodes for the ulnar motor nerve were positioned slightly closer to the first metacarpophalangeal joint. Both the second as well as third digits were connected by the median sensory nerve. A ring electrode was implanted on both the radial and ulnar borders of the finger being examined, positioned somewhat closer to the tip of the finger than its base. The distance between the active electrode and the reference electrode was 4 cm.

Lower Limb Nerve Conduction Measurements:

In both lower limbs, the sural nerve for sensory information and the peroneal and tibial nerves for motor information were assessed. To assess the sural nerve, electrodes were positioned on the lateral malleolus and calf. For peroneal nerves, electrodes were placed at the knee and ankle, and for tibial nerves, they were placed close to the tip of the fibula and ankle. Measurements were made of the motor and sensory conduction velocities, as well as the amplitude of the action potential.

Inclusion Criteria: Included were patients over the age of 18, who had been diagnosed with type 2 diabetes for at least ten years, per the WHO definition. This study comprised both male and female participants who were able and willing to provide consent for it.

Exclusion Criteria: Individuals under the age of eighteen who had type-1 diabetes or a history of peripheral neuropathy unrelated to diabetes were

not accepted. Individuals having a history of myopathies, neuromuscular disorders, hereditary neuropathy, drug-induced neuropathy, and peripheral neuropathy with a recognized cause—cerebrovascular stroke—were not included in the group.

Statistical analysis: The social science statistical programmes were used to conduct the statistical analysis (SPSS). The mean was displayed for the continuous variable and the number of instances with percentages for the categorical variables. A P-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically noteworthy. ANOVA was used to compare data between more than two groups.

Table 1: Demographic profile

	Minimum value	Maximum value	Mean $\pm$ SD
Age (years)	30	79	49.01 $\pm$ 11.49
BMI	17.3	50.1	28.71 $\pm$ 6.59
HbA1c (%)	5.7	13.0	8.01 $\pm$ 1.82
Fasting blood glucose (gm/dl)	78	406	184.79 $\pm$ 77.11

As the duration of diabetes extended to more than five years, our results demonstrated a substantial decline in both sensory and motor nerve velocities (P-value = 0.0501; P-value = 0.0031, respectively). Additionally, the results demonstrated that when the duration of diabetes increased beyond five years, there was a significant reduction in both sensory nerve amplitude (P-value = 0.0031) and

Results

There were 95 T2DM patients in this research, with a 54.7% male prevalence.

The participants ranged in age from 30 to 79 years old, with a mean age of 49 years.

The average height and weight of the subjects were 91.669 $\pm$ 3.169 kg and 169.731 $\pm$ 7.229 cm, respectively. The subjects had an average BMI of 30.561 $\pm$ 3.179 and an average HbA1c of 8.04%. [Table 1]

motor nerve amplitude (P-value = 0.0501), but there was no significant difference in the mean HbA1c between the two groups with a duration of five years. The amplitudes of the sensory and motor nerves were significantly correlated with BMI for underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obese individuals (P-value < 0.05), according to our findings. [Table 2, 3]

Table 2: Nerve velocities and amplitude among participants

Variables	<5 years (Mean $\pm$ SD)	5–10 years (Mean $\pm$ SD)	P-value
Age (years)	49.29 $\pm$ 8.11	53.21 $\pm$ 10.79	0.033
HbA1c	7.71 $\pm$ 1.59	8.19 $\pm$ 1.71	0.291
Sensory nerve velocity (m/sec)	64.069 $\pm$ 3.221	54.001 $\pm$ 5.339	0.0501
Motor nerve velocity (m/sec)	63.391 $\pm$ 2.379	53.869 $\pm$ 2.081	0.0031
Sensory nerve amplitude (mV)	25.711 $\pm$ 5.701	19.511 $\pm$ 6.52	0.0031
Motor nerve amplitude (mV)	8.789 $\pm$ 3.109	6.941 $\pm$ 1.839	0.0501

Table 3: Nerve conduction and HbA1c

Variables	HbA1c < 6 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	HbA1c > 6 (Mean $\pm$ SD)	P-value
Sensory nerve velocity (m/sec)	63.961 $\pm$ 2.359	55.489 $\pm$ 2.431	0.029
Motor nerve velocity (m/sec)	63.001 $\pm$ 2.589	51.439 $\pm$ 1.661	0.021
Sensory nerve amplitude (mV)	26.909 $\pm$ 1.261	20.849 $\pm$ 2.101	0.0509
Motor nerve amplitude (mV)	6.879 $\pm$ 3.551	6.609 $\pm$ 3.289	0.0509

Discussion

Diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN) is the most common and problematic diabetic foot consequence. Diabetic patients with symptoms and/or evidence of peripheral nerve injury are diagnosed with diabetic neuropathic pain (DN), which can be localised or diffuse, after all other possible causes have been ruled out [9, 10]. Diabetes has long been associated with neurological symptoms, regardless of its clinical range. In fact, a plethora of clinical data about the impact of diabetes on the neurological system

exists, and it is clear that involvement of the central nervous system, peripheral nervous system, and ocular symptoms are frequent and may have been documented [11]. The degree of nerve damage determines the clinical signs of DPN. It has been suggested that NCS be used to validate DPN findings [12]. According to NCS, the current investigation found that diabetic individuals with more than five years of diabetes had decreased velocity and amplitude of both sensory and motor fibres (P-value = 0.05).

These findings were consistent with a Jordanian research by Khawaja et al. that evaluated people with T2DM for five years and found that the longest duration of diabetes was the best predictor of DPN. These results showed a connection between the length of diabetes and neuropathy. However, in line with the findings of Khawaja et al. [13], our data likewise showed a significant (P -value 0.05) correlation between BMI and the motor and sensory amplitudes of both motor and sensory fibres in T2DM patients. Additionally, Zhang et al. discovered that in the diabetic groups compared to controls, the median, ulnar, posterior tibial, and common peroneal nerves had longer distal motor latency, slower sensory nerve CV, and significantly lower sensory nerve action potential and amplitude of compound muscle action potential [15].

The results of our research align with a study conducted by Mayeda et al., which concluded that continuous glucose monitoring is more effective in detecting the danger of complications, such as diabetic peripheral neuropathy (DPN), compared to haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) testing. Our results also showed that well-controlled diabetes mellitus and routine HbA1c testing can promote the prevention of neurological complications [16]. Similar results to ours were reported in another study, which demonstrated that HbA1c > 10% had lower CV and amplitude potential than HbA1c 10% [17]. The findings of Partanen et al.'s study indicated that individuals with NIDDM exhibited slower nerve conduction velocities in both sensory and motor nerves, as well as lower sensory amplitude in the radial nerve and lower motor amplitude in the median nerve.

These results align with the strong negative correlation that our study observed with type II diabetes mellitus. [18] Furthermore, in their investigation, Eman Abd El Aziz Galbat et al. discovered a link between a higher severity of DPN and inadequate glycemic management. A study on nerve conduction demonstrated a strong negative correlation between motor and sensory delay, as well as a significant positive correlation between motor and sensory conduction velocity (CV) and amplitude [19]. It is crucial for primary care physicians to inform patients, identify concerns at an early stage, and provide appropriate treatment in order to avert more severe repercussions and improve patients' quality of life.

Limitations of study: We are left with only speculation since the cross-sectional design makes it hard to examine the timing for the formation of the observed variations. Furthermore, the current study's sample size was quite limited; it could be preferable if a bigger sample is examined in the future.

Conclusion

In DN patients having nerve conduction investigations, our results examined the relationship between BMI and the length of DM, both of which were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). When combined, these results offer a crucial insight of the neurological symptoms experienced by DN patients. Our research may contribute to a better understanding of the neurological involvement in DN patients and may lead to the concept that axonal damage from a persistent inflammatory response may produce muscular weakness and neuropathic pain, which can have a significant impact on the lives of DN patients.

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